

FICTION IS A FACTOR IN THE FORMATION OF NATIONAL EDUCATION AND SPIRITUALITY IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the issues of educating children from an early age in the national spirit through fiction, encouraging them to read. It shows the ways of shaping the spirituality of the younger generation through the example of folklore and Uzbek writers.

The following words of Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhonov, a representative of the Jadid movement and one of the founders of the new national school, are still relevant today: "An educated child respects the elders. He treats her equally well. And He has mercy and blessings on **the youth** than Himself, and knows the **value** of everyone" [1; 50]. It should be noted that the phrase "an educated child respects and honors the elders" refers to the fact that a child's upbringing is formed in his childhood. Can we teach our children the right way to raise their children today ?!

Can we instill in them a national spirit, our national values? It would be great if every parent and educator could ask these questions and answer them with pleasure. We are convinced of the truth of U. Chen's

statement that "raising a child requires deeper observation and deeper wisdom than governing the state"

The fact that the upbringing of children in our country is considered to be a deeper issue than the governance of the state is reflected in the fact that our government is taking special and permanent measures. President Mirziyoyev said: "No matter what sector we take, we cannot achieve any change and a prosperous life without training modern specialists. The training of such personnel, the healthy gene pool of the nation, begins, first of all, with the system of pre-school education "[3], - he said.

Kindergarten education is a period of mastering their complex movements, developing basic hygiene, cultural and

labor skills, developing speech, and forming the first buds of social morality and aesthetic taste. According to the famous Russian pedagogue Lesgaft, the period of human kindergarten is a stage in which children develop patterns of character and the foundations of moral character [4, 18].

At a time when parents are preoccupied with their marital worries, filling in any gaps in the quality of child rearing and education in the family places a huge responsibility on professionals at all levels of continuing education.

The pre-school education system in our country is the primary, the most basic link of continuing education. Therefore, educators of preschool education organizations (MTT) should provide their students with quality, meaningful, and most importantly, interesting and non-boring activities for the child.

It is important to ensure that the child's impressions and outcomes continue in speech, movement, and mood after returning to their family. The literature on the subject of our article has a wide range of possibilities and needs.

Preschool educational institutions regularly hold a variety of poems, songs and action games for our time and for future generations. But how it is organized depends on the skill of the teacher.

In our opinion, if children are taught to recite, memorize, and explain various poems that are easy for them to memorize and do not have difficulty in speech (consisting of simple words), the child will feel happy and will be able to read words through fluent pronunciation, fluency in speech, strengthening of memory, ability to express the tone appropriate to the content

of the poem, a sense of perception and national-moral upbringing are formed.

The educator of the preschool organization should be well aware that the choice of poems based on the age of the child and the fact that the poem is recited in a cheerful tone, the simplicity of the words is of great importance. Because if a child chooses poems that are not specific to his age, he will get tired of memorizing and reciting them, and then his interest in memorizing other poems will disappear. What's worse is the words that I can spell I often mistype.

Each age group in preschool has its own set of tasks for speech development. As they get older, their level of acceptance of the various poems taught by their tutor will increase, and they will gradually become more complex. In this way, children develop the ability to listen to poetry. Therefore, adults need to be aware of children's age opportunities.

Early childhood children's acceptance of works of art is based on their emotional response to them, their perception of different tones, their attitude, their ability to recognize and care for the characters of the work as much as possible. For children of this age, small-scale poetry, that is, folklore and authorial poetry, is important. Children are especially interested in playful poems, the main characters of which are children and animals.

Together with adults, the child enthusiastically organizes games based on the plots of proverbs and countless poems, listening to sound imitations and rhythmic repetitions in the direction of folklore. The child takes the events described in literary works very seriously. He is also ready to

listen to his favorite fairy tales and poetic tales several times.

This is the basis for the writing of national spirituality in the minds of children: the desire for knowledge is awakened, national identity is introduced, a sense of respect for national values is nurtured. Below, we decided to give some examples of what preschool educators can select and memorize for children in their classes.

Hamza's book "About School" from the book "Light Literature" is of special importance for children of preschool education:

School is the sun of the nation, School is the palace of the nation

Maybe an eyebrow **of it**. The place of science and etiquette.

The happiest person in the world without eyes and eyebrows

What an ugly head **it has**. The place of seekers.

As children recite this poem, their first impressions of school will be enriched, and their desire to grow up, go to school, and learn will increase.

The poem "School" from the book "The Second Teacher" by A. Avloni also serves to educate, to shape children's desire to explore the school in beautiful, bright colors, to study, to become literate:

School is a pearl, School makes you human,
School will open Paradise for you, School
will give you modesty,
School escapes ignorance, School destroys
grief,

Study hard, boy! Study hard, boy!

H.Olimjon's poem "Vatan" helps children to form a feeling of boundless love for their

hometown, a sense of hometown, love and respect for the motherland:

My joy is unbounded

I have endless happiness.

It made me happy

This is my invincible Motherland.

It should be noted that in addition to Uzbek folk tales, it is important for preschoolers to read a number of works by children's artists. In particular, H. Olimjon's works such as "Semurg", "Aigul and Bakhtiyor", Shukur Sadulla's "The old man and the wolf" are written in a poetic way, and children can listen to them with interest.

The Uzbek national mentality reflected in them is gradually taking root in the minds of young poets. In this way, they are taught to know and understand the unique examples of Uzbek literature. Z.Diyor's poem "Butterfly" is also important in that it forms in children such relationships as love of mother nature, its preservation, feeling of beauty:

Hey butterfly, butterfly, never run away
from me,

Your wings are like silk. I know a friend.

You fly so fast, You fly so fast,

Let me tell you - it was a scary place.

Another of the poet's poems, "Sniper", inspires children to grow up faster, to love the military profession, to defend their hometown like a brother:

Friends, when I grow up,

I'm going to the army.

Who is as killed wrestler

There ill take my brother.

Quds Muhammadi's poem "Hashar" also evokes children's first impressions of the hashar, which is unique to our Uzbek nation. A feeling of love and respect is formed. In the circle of his family, in the processes mentioned in the poem, they start to work by reciting the verses aloud:

Come on guys, whoever it is,
Come on, guys, let's get on with it.
Brothers and sisters, **we plant seedlings.**
All children, don't miss the opportunity.

Elijah Muslim's poem "The Decent Girl" also instills in children such concepts as teaching girls to work hard, helping parents with household chores:

Rana is still young, she keeps the house tidy,

Everyone is amazed at his work. Never on a dusty couch.

A small broom in hand, Neighbors see it
Porcelain courtyard, porch... Praise sooner or later.

In conclusion, if the educators of preschool education institutions enrich their lessons with such poems, the formation of spiritual and moral qualities of preschool children will be observed. Children's spiritual qualities such as fluency, memory, expressive poetry reading, listening skills, responsiveness, activity, self-confidence, love of poetry, sense of beauty are developed. There is a desire to act like the heroes in the poems he remembers. This passion, in turn, plays a key role in learning and being active in the later stages of education.

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